

TOWARDS HEALTHIER TECH INTERACTIONS: DESIGN FOR BEHAVIOUR CHANGE TO PREVENT THE NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF TECHNOLOGY OVERUSE

Alessia Buffagni

Dr, Università Iuav di Venezia, ITALY, abuffagni@iuav.it

Abstract

The technological devices have permeated every aspect of modern life, introducing significant changes in human behaviors and social interaction patterns. However, the constant, sometimes compulsive, use of such devices has triggered a series of negative consequences, evident both physically and psychologically. From a postural standpoint, for instance, the prolonged habit of using smartphones, tablets, and computers has contributed to the onset of musculoskeletal disorders. From a sensory perspective, the visual and auditory hyperstimulation resulting from continuous use of technological devices has led to a decline in sensory perception. On the cognitive front, excessive exposure to digital screens has been shown to negatively affect attention, memory, and learning abilities. And on the behavioral side, excessive dependence on technological devices has fueled compulsive behaviors with manifestations of digital addiction and sleep disturbances.

The question then arises: what contribution can Product Design make to prevent or slow down the onset of these disorders? Can Design intervene by modifying people's incorrect behaviors towards technological devices? This paper tries to provide answers to these questions by proposing a first development of healthy/supportive solutions adaptable to the most advanced technologies on the market. The adopted approach is that of Design for Behavior Change, which aims to positively influence people's behavior through the design of products and services. By understanding the motivations and incentives that drive people's actions, design can mitigate undesirable behaviors and promote healthy ones for the individual, society, and the environment. The object of design is therefore behavior itself, implemented through actively changing user attitudes through the use of products and artifacts.

Keywords: product design, behavior change, design for health, technological devices

1 INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of technological devices has brought about significant changes in human behaviors and social interaction patterns. However, the constant and sometimes compulsive utilization of these devices has resulted in a series of adverse consequences, evident both physically and psychologically (Gupta, 2023), particularly among children and young adults (Ricci et al., 2021; Rosen et al., 2014; Hawi & Samaha, 2016; Thomée et al., 2012). Research indicates that prolonged use of devices such as smartphones and laptops can lead to poor posture, resulting in neck, shoulder, and back pain, commonly known as *text neck* or *tech neck* (Kumari et al., 2021). Additionally, excessive screen time often correlates with reduced physical activity, increasing the risk of obesity, cardiovascular disease, and other health issues, including eyestrain, dry eyes, and headaches, collectively known as *computer vision syndrome* (Lema et al., 2022).

Constant connectivity and exposure to social media can contribute to feelings of anxiety and stress, as individuals may feel pressured to keep up with online activities and social comparisons. Excessive screen time, particularly late at night, can disrupt sleep patterns and contribute to depression and mood disorders (Boers et al., 2019). Moreover, heavy reliance on technology can lead to decreased attention spans, reduced ability to concentrate, and difficulties with memory and cognitive functions (Hawi & Samaha, 2016).

Furthermore, excessive use of digital technology, especially social media, may result in social withdrawal and isolation as individuals spend more time online and less time engaging in face-to-face interactions (Kushlev et al., 2019). Some individuals develop problematic behaviors, such as internet addiction or gaming addiction, which can interfere with daily functioning and relationships (Rashwan et al., 2023). Additionally, impaired communication skills are reported: over-reliance on digital communication methods like texting and messaging can hinder the development of effective verbal communication skills and interpersonal relationships (Takeuchi et al., 2018).

According to Fasoli (2021), Digital Overuse can be explained by several psychological theories. One of these is Self-Determination Theory (SDT), which explains that the appeal of digital media lies in their ability to fulfill fundamental needs such as learning and social connection, and that excessive satisfaction of these needs online can lead to media overuse. At the same time, the overuse of technologies can be attributed to the gratification they provide users through pleasant stimuli and rewards, often exceeding users' expectations. This, in turn, generates digital stress, which can stem from managing a vast amount of online information and communication. In summary, the attractiveness of digital media, the gratification derived from overuse, and digital stress are key factors contributing to Digital Overuse. Additionally, part of the appeal of many digital products may be attributed to the economic model dominating the internet, which involves exploiting user data for profit. Certainly, these theories are not exhaustive; further research is needed to fully understand these dynamics and identify additional causes of Digital Overuse (Fasoli, 2021).

Considering these premises, and acknowledging that we will increasingly interact with a variety of technological products—whether wearable, portable, mobile, fixed, or holographic—and recognizing that their regular and prolonged use will impact both our physiology and behavior, leading to long-term physical, sensory, and cognitive changes; can today's designers effectively devise strategies to prevent, slow down, or alleviate the probable long-term degenerative effects stemming from the continual and pervasive use of evolving entertainment and communication media? What role can Product Design play in mitigating or slowing down the onset of these disorders? Can Design effectively modify people's problematic behaviors towards technological devices? This paper seeks to address these inquiries by proposing an initial development of healthy and supportive solutions adaptable to the latest technologies available. The chosen approach is that of Design for Behavior Change, which aims to positively influence individuals' behavior through the design of products and services (Niedderered et al., 2017). By comprehending the motivations and incentives driving people's actions, design can alleviate undesirable behaviors and foster healthy ones for both the individual and society, while also considering environmental impacts (Khadilkar & Cash, 2020). Therefore, the focus of design lies in behavior itself, achieved by actively altering user attitudes through the use of products and artifacts.

2 METHODOLOGY

As above mentioned, Design for Behaviour Change is the chosen approach. Defined by Cash, Hartlev and Durazo (2017) as: *designing for antecedent behaviour change strategies using implicit interventions to impact behaviour*, the aim is to design products, systems, or interventions that influence and facilitate positive changes in human behavior, seeking to address various societal challenges by leveraging design principles and methodologies to encourage individuals to adopt healthier, more sustainable, or socially desirable behaviors. The goal is to promote behavior change by ethically evoking, nudging, persuading or motivating people, leading to positive outcomes for individuals, communities, and society as a whole (Khadilkar and Cash, 2020; Thaler & Sustein, 2008). One of the strategies that fall within this approach is the Theory of Nudge, as conceptualized by Thaler and Sustein (2008) as *any aspect of choice architecture that alters people's behavior in a predictable way, without forbidding any option or significantly changing economic incentives*. Essentially, this involves influencing or guiding people's behavior for their presumed benefit, albeit without imposing excessive restrictions on their freedom (libertarian paternalism).

This approach was implemented within the framework of a 20-hour workshop with master's students in product design at the University Luav of Venice (Italy). The workshop, entitled "Design for the Future Body," aimed to identify and comprehend some of the detrimental behaviors resulting from excessive digital usage and to formulate an initial framework for healthy and supportive solutions adaptable to contemporary technologies. The Behavioral Design process employed follows the model outlined by Cash, Hartlev, and Durazo (2017), which entails a stage-gate sequence transitioning from divergent phases, focusing on exploring and defining behavior, to convergent phases, aimed at influencing behavior. The initial phase comprises two primary stages: *behavior mapping* and *fieldwork*, commencing with *Problem/Need Definition*. The subsequent phase involves *intervention development*, guided by *iterative testing* and *refinement*.

However, due to time limitations (20-hour workshop), conducting the iterative testing and refinement phase was not feasible. Consequently, students proceeded with the development of the design concept using study models.

3 RESULTS

The design concepts presented below primarily embrace the strategy outlined in the Nudge theory: to qualify as a mere nudge, the intervention must be easily avoidable and entail minimal costs. The following healthy/supportive design proposals tackle issues such as: incorrect posture during computer work (3.1), eye and vision problems arising from exposure to blue light emitted by computer screens (3.2), and disruption of the circadian rhythm due to prolonged smartphone use before sleep (3.3). While the identified problems may be interconnected, because they often arise from similar root causes or contribute to each other's exacerbation (e.g. incorrect posture while working at the computer can lead to strain on the eyes, neck, and shoulders, contributing to discomfort and potential vision problems; prolonged exposure to blue light from computer screens can disrupt the circadian rhythm, impacting sleep quality; disruption of the circadian rhythm due to prolonged smartphone use before sleep can lead to tiredness and difficulty maintaining proper posture during computer work, exacerbating existing issues), the proposed solutions are designed to accommodate various contexts and times of the day. By addressing one aspect of these interconnected problems, the aim is to positively influence others.

3.1 Ergo, a portable *nudging* posture assistant

Ergo (Fig.1) is an intelligent device designed to prevent text neck syndrome. This condition occurs when the head tilts forward towards the computer screen (Fig.2), significantly increasing the strain on the spine as the degree of tilt varies. The consequences may include muscle pain, spine pain, discopathies, and cervical-dorsal contractures. Ergo's primary objective is to monitor and promote correct posture, with a focus on young students and professionals who frequently use PCs. The device utilizes a camera to detect the user's posture and provides feedback through either musical or silent modes, depending on the context. In music mode, user-selected songs play with volume proportional to the correctness of the posture (the volume decreases, or even mutes, if the user adopts an incorrect posture), while silent mode offers visual feedback on the screen. Additionally, the assistant sends alerts for breaks and suggests preventive exercises, such as neck rotations, lateral flexions, and alternate movements (Fig. 2). Its compact size and lightweight design facilitate easy portability, allowing users to maintain correct posture regardless of location. The product aims to influence behavior change through nudges, promoting a healthier lifestyle and preventing text neck syndrome.

Figure 1. *Ergo*, designed by Giovanni Campanale, Silvia Locaputo, Arianna Tura.

Figure 2. *Ergo*, storyboard of use.

3.2 Iride, smart cam for *computer vision syndrome* prevention

Iride (Fig.3) is an intelligent camera equipped with an e-ink screen designed for digital workers who spend prolonged hours in front of screens, aiming to prevent eye damage associated with computer vision syndrome (eyestrain, headaches, blurred vision, dry eyes, neck and shoulder pain) through exercises that stimulate the visual field. Iride is compact, lightweight, and installed on the upper edge of the PC screen. After approximately 20 minutes of PC use, a suggestion appears on the e-ink display to divert attention from the screen and engage in simple eye and focus exercises, such as observing the weather outside (Fig. 4) or identifying a colored object in the room. This approach emphasizes proactive measures rather than solely managing symptoms, and users are not obligated to perform the exercises. Instead, they are encouraged and ideally nudged by a sense of responsibility regarding their health, gradually fostering a positive habit.

Figure 3. *Iride*, designed by Nicolò De Bortoli, Vittorio Schembari.

Figure 4. *Iride* mock up on a PC screen displaying 'What's the weather like today?' in Italian.

3.3 Nenna, assistive device for circadian rhythm

Nenna (Fig.5) is a device designed to enhance sleep quality and improve the overall well-being of both young and adult users. Developed in response to the detrimental effects of excessive smartphone usage before bedtime, this product offers a multisensory solution to regulate the sleep-wake cycle. By integrating soothing sounds, calming fragrances, and specific lighting for different sleep stages, the device establishes an ideal environment to facilitate relaxation. Its design allows for the accommodation of a smartphone, functioning similar to a standard docking station. In addition to its relaxation features, which activate only when the smartphone is placed on top (detected via a piezoelectric pressure sensor), the device includes a bedside clock/alarm function and charging base. Sound, scent, lights, and alarm functionalities are all customizable through the associated app. Similarly to the above presented concepts, a nudge is employed: until the user places the smartphone atop the device, the relaxation experience aimed at promoting sleep cannot commence, yet the choice is not mandated. Ultimately, it is left to the user to determine whether and when to initiate the relaxation experience. Through proper usage, the user's improper behavior will gradually be addressed.

Figure 5. *Nenna*, designed by Giulia Abbattista, Francesca Facciolongo, Pietro Palazzo.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents three examples of healthy and supportive solutions devised during the 20-hour workshop. These are product design concepts crafted to encourage behavioral corrections through *nudges* to adapt to the technologies currently available on the market (smartphone, laptop). Undoubtedly, the designed functions could be integrated into future upgrades of the same products. As of today, users can already set time limits for the usage of specific apps, after which the app will be blocked or restricted, or disable notifications during certain periods, helping users to focus on other activities. Regarding PCs, monitors already have brightness adjustment functions to adapt to ambient light conditions and reduce eye strain, blue light filters, and notifications suggesting users to take regular breaks. The Big Tech companies have already begun to pay attention to the health and well-being of their users; therefore, the research focus that we propose and its potential outcomes are of undeniable interest. Integrating preventive technology into their bestsellers to reassure users (and even more so, users' parents) about the benefits, or reduction of long-term risks associated with their use, is an operation that would appeal to marketing sectors for obvious reasons, especially if followed by clinical certification from medical specialists involved in the design phase. At present, we provide an initial modest response to the research questions (*can today's designers effectively devise strategies to prevent, slow down, or alleviate the probable long-term degenerative effects stemming from the continual and pervasive use of evolving entertainment and communication media? What role can Product Design play in mitigating or slowing down the onset of these disorders? Can Design effectively modify people's problematic behaviors towards technological devices?*) with the aim not only of addressing a matter of significant global interest and raising awareness among young designers but also as an exercise in designing technological products by applying the Design for Behavior Change approach. Designers cannot single-handedly solve the complex issues associated with technology overuse—behavioral psychologists, medical professionals, technologists, end-users (co-design), corporate stakeholders must be involved in the design process—, they can certainly contribute to mitigating its negative impacts through thoughtful and intentional design choices. By prioritizing user well-being and incorporating features that promote healthy behaviors, designers can help individuals develop more balanced relationships with technology and reduce the risk of long-term adverse effects.

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